

THE PROBLEM OF POLYSEMY IN LINGUISTIC TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation: The article analyzes the polysemy – phenomenon of linguistic terminology. The criteria of differentiation such related phenomena as evisemy and polysemy by analyzing the terms of linguistics were allocated.

Keywords: polysemy; evisemy; linguistic terminology.

The problem of ambiguity is the subject of controversy among philologists. Most of them define the phenomenon of eurysemia as a variation of the lexical semantics of a high degree of generalization, which combines words with a broad conceptual basis. Not all linguists support the opinion about the autonomy of this linguistic category and the possibility of its opposition to polysemy.

An analysis of scientific works devoted to the study of eurysemy shows that the semantic structure of eurysemantic words is mainly considered in two opposite directions: 1) eurysemy and polysemy are considered separate independent categories (N. N. Amosova [1], I. V. Arnold [3], L. Ya. Grosul [5], T. V. Zhukova [8], V. Ya. Plotkin [13], etc.); 2) broad meaning is considered as a characteristic of one of the lexico-semantic variants of a polysemantic word (S. N. Dimova [7], G. I. Gurskaya [6], etc.). The problems of developing clear criteria for distinguishing between these two linguistic phenomena, the features of revealing the semantic shades of eurysemic and polysemantic words in speech, etc., have not yet been studied.

The definition of the concept of “broad-meaning” (“eurysemia”) was first proposed by N. N. Amosov: “Broad-semantic is a linguistic phenomenon of the lexico-semantic level, which is characterized by the expansion of the semantic volume of a word to denote various denotations” [1, p. 114]. However, unlike polysemantic words, eurysemantic words are characterized by structural single-conceptuality. Designated concepts are only externally connected with the word, with its phonetic shell, but are not included in the structure of meaning. They appear during the functioning of the word in specific speech contexts and correlate with a single generalized broad concept.

The purpose of our article is to analyze and identify criteria for distinguishing related phenomena by ontological status - polysemy and its types. The object of research is the terminology of linguistics.

Let's analyze the phenomenon of eurysemia using the example of the linguistic term word, which is "the basic minimal semantic unit of the language" (MPE, p. 382). In linguistics, this metaterm can be called any lexical unit: Ukrainian. antonym, synonym, homonym, biblicalism, derivative, historicism, occasionalism, homophone, polonism, etc.

All of the listed lexical units, designated by the term word, are included in the scope of its nomination, since the differential features of its semantic structure are minimized, and therefore correlate with an almost unlimited range of denotations given by the context, which confirms the fact that "the meaning of the word is based on broad semantics lies the most generalized and abstract sign, on the basis of which this word becomes semantically compatible with all objects and phenomena that have this sign" [9, p. 12].

Proponents of a different point of view on eurysemia distinguish eurysemical LSV (sometimes more than one) as part of the semantic structure of a lexical unit that is polysemantic in nature. In their opinion, broad meaning is not only the content side of the most general, abstract lexico-semantic variant of a polysemantic word [4].

The coexistence of two views on the nature of broad-meaning language units makes it difficult to find the specifics of their semantic meaning and to distinguish between the concepts of broad-meaning and polysemy.

Considering the above, some researchers conditionally distinguish lexemes into monosemic (with one meaning), multi-valued (with a significant but not excessive number of meanings) and broad-valued (with an abnormally large number of meanings) [12, p. 102].

It is believed that the word at the stage of its formation and consolidation in the language is monosemic, but its meaning can expand over time by imposing various realities of the surrounding reality. As a result, it becomes either polysemantic or broad-meaningful. In the first case, on the basis of the original value, as a result of associative transfer, related but different values arise that differ from each other.

In the second case, the meaning of the original word is transformed, becoming more and more abstract, and the word passes into the category of semantically "developed" lexemes. L.P. Kudrevatykh classifies lexical units with a narrow and broad meaning as a monosemic type [10, p. 35], which confirms our assumption about the different nature of the expansion of the meaning of polysemantic and broad-meaning words.

The meaning of the former can be conditionally called discrete, because they consist of many separate meanings differentiated by the context, and the meaning of the others can be called continual, since the eurysemant brings its unique meaning to any context.

Thus, if we consider the phenomenon of eurysemy according to the first version of its definition, when a wide-ranging word has a single generalized meaning, then wide-ranging seems to us to be a fairly common phenomenon in linguistic terminology. From this point of view, eurysemia is especially characteristic of general linguistic terms, in the seme composition of which we observe only one seme of a generalized, non-special nature, for example: Ukr. denotation, part of the movie, word, element, system, method, sign, etc.

In some lexicographic works, these terms are recorded mainly as unambiguous. Wed : denotation “denoted object” (KTSLT, p. 201); parts of movi “grammatical classes of words that have common features” (MFE, p. 439); the word “the minimum meaningful unit of the language, which is freely reproduced in the language and serves to build sentences” (KTSLT, p. 166); method “method, technique, methodology for the study of linguistic phenomena” (KTSLT, p. 88); a sign “two-sided formation, which is the unity of the mental content (meaning) and the sound (or graphic) form-determinant” (KTSLT, p. 65).

According to our observations, these terms in dictionaries “acquire an abstract character, combine an indefinite number of denotations, generating the emergence of eurysemia” [2, p. 85]; however, these words will be related to a certain denotation only in the context, in the process of their functioning. On the example of the work of A. A. Potebnya “Thought and Language”, G. V. Mayorov observes how the term “word” correlates with many denotations, that is, it is broadly meaningful.

The researcher cites fragments of a scientific text: “[Word], which springs from the depths of human nature, is a means of creating <...> ideas; a person would not create songs, poems, if every word of his was not a poetic work; the word < ... > is the organ of thought; thought is nourished by the word; only this makes it possible for the word to be passed on from generation to generation; the word lives only when it is spoken, < ... > the word is poetry; the word < ... > is a symbol, an ideal and has all the properties of a work of art” [11, p. 180].

It can be seen from the above quotation that the semantics of the linguistic term word is much broader in the context of the work of A. A. Potebnya; the definition from the lexicographic source is only the tip of the lexico-semantic “iceberg”, because in scientific discourse the term word as a linguistic unit

reveals such conceptual meanings as: "language", "work of art", "thought" and many other metaphorical and associative rethinking.

From another point of view, broad meaning is only the content of the most general, abstract lexico-semantic variant of a polysemantic word.

In our opinion, such a vision of broadness fully justifies itself, because in linguistic terminology you can find examples of "such" wide-valued terms. Cf., for example, the meaning of terms in which wide-digit LSVs are emphasized: language is "a complex social phenomenon in which the following features are distinguished: a) the most important means of human communication and unification of people into a community; b) means of self-identification and expression of the mentality of the nation (ethnic group); c) a means of forming and developing thought, carrying out cognitive activity, implementing the spiritual culture of the people, "" a system of socially conscious sound and letter-reproducible signs that function according to certain regulations, norms and are implemented in the sound and semantic substance of specific speech acts of communication, " "a certain information system performing a natural language function or functioning as a substitute" (CTSLLT, p. 92); morphological category - "the category of words combined by the same forms of expression of grammatical meanings"; "a generalized grammatical characteristic of a certain word category, expressed in the ratio of word forms of this category or in the contrast of grammatical forms of the same word"; "affixal varieties of words expressing grammatical categories of this category of words" (CTSLLT, p. 97); paradigm - "a system of inflective changes that serve as a model of shaping for a certain part of speech"; "a collection of forms of inflection of the same word"; "in the broad sense - grouping of units of one language system or subsystem into classes based on their different oppositions; a series of contrasted language units, each determined by relation to the other units "; "specific word usage of the token in their syntagmatic connections";

The examples of linguistic terms discussed have several meanings, among which a broad meaning can be distinguished in the semantic structure of each term. "A broad meaning is such a LSV, in the structure of which there are seeds with the maximum degree of generalization, which are specified in speech" [1, p. 114]. Thus, the main marker of eurysemia is the identification of extremely generalized and abstracted features, thanks to which one term can refer to many objects and phenomena of environmental reality.

So, the phenomenon of ambiguity is sufficiently characteristic of linguistic terminology. One of the common types of polysemia of terms is eurysemia, the

characteristics of which are the marginal generalization of meaning, syncretism, a relatively high frequency of use, polydenotativity, semantic generalization, give every reason to believe that it is inappropriate to "confuse" eurysemia with ambiguity, and define it as an adjacent phenomenon. Eurysemia as an ambiguous phenomenon in terminology occupies 1.2% of the total number of terms.

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